

A Hospital Based Clinical and Investigative Study in Females with Diffuse Hair Loss

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Abstract:

Background: Diffuse hair loss is a very common condition for which female patients present to dermatology OPD. Adequate management of DHL requires detailed history, physical examination and screening for various laboratory parameters to define the contributing factors.

Methods: One hundred and thirty- three females with diffuse hair loss were included in the study. Thorough history, clinical examination & bedside tests were done in all study subjects. All the patients were tested for complete hemogram, serum Vit B12, serum Vit D3, TSH, serum ferritin and selected patients for serum LH, serum FSH, serum prolactin and serum testosterone levels.

Results: Among 133 patients, 73 patients (54.88%) presented with acute telogen effluvium (ATE), 42 patients (31.57%) with chronic telogen effluvium (CTE) and 18 patients (13.53%) with female patterned hair loss. Incidence of FPHL were highest in the age group of 41-60 whereas CTE in 25-40 years. Specific etiological factors for acute telogen effluvium were found in 79.36% patients. In majority of these patients (31.50%), severe anemia (<8gm/dL) was the contributory factor followed by febrile illness (30.13%). Serum ferritin level was significantly lower in ATE & CTE group as compared to FPHL group (p = 0.006).

Conclusion: Nonscarring diffuse alopecia can be caused by multiple factors. Serum ferritin, serum TSH, serum vitamin B12 and D3 levels seem to have a contributing role in the pathogenesis of hair loss, and their supplementation may be required for the faster hair growth in nonscarring DHL.

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Introduction

Hair is an ectodermal structure, and its development begins at the 8th week of life. Hair follicles undergo a repetitive sequence of growth and rest known as the hair cycle. Five phases of the hair cycle are growth phase (anagen I-VI), regression phase (catagen), resting phase (telogen), shedding phase (exogen), and lag phase (kenogen). Anything that interrupts the normal hair cycle of hair growth can diffuse hair loss [1]. Normal hair cycle results in replacement of every hair on the scalp by 3-5 years [2]. Hair loss is a common distressing condition. Diffuse hair loss is a common complaint encountered by dermatologists in their daily clinical practice [3]. Women present more frequently with this complaint. The prevalence of diffuse hair loss among females was estimated to be higher in the age group of 20 years and above. Diffuse hair loss usually occurs without any inflammation or scarring [2]. There are various causes for diffuse hair loss, which include telogen effluvium (TE), female pattern hair loss (FPHL),

chronic telogen effluvium (CTE), anagen effluvium (AE), loose anagen hair syndrome and diffuse type of alopecia areata. The incidence of telogen effluvium is not well determined due to a lack of data, especially in subclinical cases [5, 6, 7]. DHL can be classified as scarring and non-scarring. Only non-scarring comes under the scope of our study, which is further classified as Telogen effluvium: It is a form of diffuse, nonscarring hair loss that occurs as a result of an abnormal shift in follicular cycling that leads to the premature shedding of hair, which is usually less than 50 percent of scalp hair [8]. Telogen effluvium can be acute (lasting < 6 months), chronic (6 months or more), or chronic-repetitive, in which CTE is punctuated by additional episodes of acute hair loss as a result of multiple intermittent triggers [9]. A wide variety of endogenous and exogenous factors have been linked to the induction of telogen effluvium, such as acute or chronic major illness, childbirth, significant emotional stress, nutritional

changes, endocrine disorders, drugs, and inflammatory conditions of the scalp: infectious conditions that affect the scalp.

Hair loss should not be looked upon as merely a complaint of cosmetic concern. This may be a pointer to various systemic illnesses like anemia, hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, chronic infectious diseases, etc. Hence, determining the cause of diffuse hair loss is mandatory in all cases [8]. Therefore, this study aimed to detect various causes of diffuse alopecia among female patients and their association with other systemic diseases and relevant laboratory parameters in this part of the country.

Material and Methods

This hospital-based observational and investigative study was done on female patients aged 12 years and older presenting with complaints of diffuse hair loss to the skin OPD at the Department of Dermatology, Venereology, and Leprosy, Government Medical College, Jammu, over a period of 1 year extending from 1st November 2020 to 31st October 2021. The patients were selected as per the following inclusion and exclusion criteria after taking written and informed consent:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Females of age 12 years and older
- With appreciable diffuse loss of hair on examination.
- Who gives the history of DHL (approx.)
- >100 hair/day for >1 month or decrease in hair density)
- Who gives the history of diffuse hair loss along with the history of previous major illness, psychological stress, major febrile illness, childbirth, surgical history, chronic blood loss, poor nutrition, etc.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Females with scarring alopecia (Focal & Diffuse).
- Females less than 12 years of age.
- Patients who are not willing to participate.

Methodology:

The demographic profile along with clinical presentation related to hair loss was taken and noted on a proforma. A detailed history was taken with special queries regarding major febrile illness, psychological stress, or history of a child in the recent past. History of chronic blood loss, poor nutrition, family history of patterned hair loss in females, and treatment history in the form of chemotherapy or any other medications were noted.

Examination

Selected patients underwent a general physical examination, followed by a gross hair and scalp examination for type of hair loss, hair thinning, temporal recession, and a hair pull test (approximately 50-60 hairs are grasped between the thumb, index, and middle fingers from the base of the hairs near the scalp and firmly but not forcefully tugged away from the scalp and examined under a light microscope to identify the type of hair by examining the roots and for any shaft abnormalities). If more than 10% of the hairs are pulled away from the scalp, this constitutes a positive pull test and implies active hair shedding. Afterwards, the scalp was thoroughly examined with a dermatoscope for type of hair (terminal/vellus), density, texture, degree, and pattern of hair loss, single follicular units, and perifollicular pigmentation among different anatomic areas of the scalp. All the patients were tested for complete hemogram, PBF, serum Vit B12, serum Vit D3, TSH, serum ferritin, and selected patients for serum LH, serum FSH, serum prolactin, and serum testosterone levels.

Figure 1: Equipment Used: 1. Phone 2. Dermoscope 3. Ice Cap 4. Uuivenal Sma1-tphone Adapter
Statistical Methods

The recorded data was compiled, entered in a spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel), and labelled properly under the various factors studied for the subjects. Thereafter, data was processed and was imported to IBM SPSS Version 26.0. The data was summarized, and descriptive statistics were

obtained and expressed as mean ± SD for the continuous variable and for categorical variables as frequencies and percentages.

Results and Observations: A total of 133 patients were evaluated in the OPD of the Department of Dermatology, all presenting with the chief complaint of diffuse hair loss.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Study Patients

Age Group (Years)	N	Percentage (%)
Adolescent (12-19)	21	15.8
Pre-adulthood (20-24)	32	24.1
Early Adulthood (25-40)	49	36.8
Late Adulthood (41-60)	29	21.8
Elderly (60+)	2	1.5
Total	133	100

The age of patients enrolled in our study ranged from 15 to 61 years, with a mean age of 36.66 ± 10.026 years. The majority of the patients were in the age group 25-40 years (36.8%).

In our study, out of 133 patients, there were 73 patients (54.88%) presenting with acute telogen effluvium, 42 patients (31.57%) with chronic telogen effluvium, and 18 patients (13.53%) with

female pattern hair loss.

Further, among the patients with acute telogen effluvium, the majority were in the age group 20-24 years (34.2%), among chronic telogen effluvium, the majority were in the age group 25-40 years (50%), and among female pattern hair loss, the majority were in the age group 41-60 years (61.1%).

Figure 2: Type of Hair Loss Distribution

In our study, Pityriasis capitis was observed in 38.1% of the patients with CTE, which was comparable with the patients of ATE and FPHL, where it was observed in 32.9% and 16.7% of the patients, respectively. (p=0.35).

History of having a COVID-19 infection was present in 26% of the patients with ATE, which was significantly higher as compared to patients with FPHL (11.1%) and CTE (7.1%). (p=0.029).

History of menstrual abnormality was present in 22.2% of the patients with FPHL, which was comparable with the patients with ATE and CTE, where it was noted in 6.9% and 9.5% of the patients, respectively. (p 0.22).

Further, family history of diffuse hair loss was present in 66.7% of the patients with FPHL, which was significantly higher as compared to patients with CTE (2.4%) and ATE (7.1%). (p=0.01).

Figure 3: Comparison of history of associated complaints in the patients with DIHL

In our study, the hair pull test was positive in 65 patients (48.87%). Further, the pull test was positive in 57 patients (78.1%) with acute telogen effluvium and 2 patients (4.76%) with chronic telogen effluvium and negative in all the patients with FPHL.

Figure 4: Hair pull test results

In our study, all the patients with FPHL showed hair shaft variability of more than 20%, vellus hair, and hair follicles with single hair in the frontal scalp. These were also the diagnostic findings of FPHL. In our study, it was found that laboratory parameters such as hemoglobin levels, S. ferritin,

S. vitamin B12, and Semm Vit D3 were observed to be lower than the normal values in the majority of patients with ATE, CTE, and FPHL, whereas S. TSH was observed to be higher than the normal value in 37% of patients with ATE, 31% with CTE, and 27.8% of the patients with FPHL.

Table 2: Hormonal assays in FPHL patients

Hormonal assay		Ludwig scaling		
		I	II	III
S. testo	Normal	7	3	1
	High	2	5	0
S.LH	Normal	4	4	0
	High	5	4	1

Further, among 18 females with FPHL, 1 patient had Ludwig scale I severity in the form of significant vertex balding, while Ludwig scale II and III severity were seen in 9 and 8 patients, respectively.

Table 3: Probable etiological factors for acute telogen effluvium in the study subjects

Probable etiological cause	N	(%) age
Febrile illness	22	30.13
Psychological stress	5	6.8
Telogen gravidarum	3	4.10
Surgical operation/blood loss	1	1.36
Severe anemia	23	31.50
Poor nutrition	4	5.47

Specific etiological factors for acute telogen effluvium were found in 79.36% of patients, while in 20.64% of patients no definite cause could be found. In the majority of the patients (31.50%), severe anemia (<8 g/dL) was the controlling factor, followed by febrile illness (30.13%), psychological sickness (6.8%), poor nutrition (5.47%), telogen gravidarum (4.10%), and surgical operation/blood loss (1.36%).

Figure 5: Probable etiological factors for telogen effluvium in the study subjects

The association of laboratory parameters with different types of diffuse hair loss showed that there was no significant difference between hemoglobin levels, serum vitamins. B12, serum vitamin D3, and serum TSH among patients with ATE, CTE, and FPHL. Whereas, serum ferritin in ATE was 20.10 ± 17.41 and CTE was 23.96 ± 16.50 , which was significantly lower than in patients with FPHL (36.73 ± 30.14). ($p = 0.006$).

Further, the association of laboratory parameters with severity of FPHL showed that there was no significant difference between hemoglobin levels, serum ferritin, and serum vitamin. D3, serum TSH,

serum testosterone, and serum LH in patients with Ludwig (I), (II), and (III). Whereas, serum Vit B12 in L(I) was 146.44 ± 99.83 , L(II) was 188.87 ± 102.75 was significantly lower than the patients with patients with L(III) with mean 642 ($p = 0.001$), serum FSH in L(I) was 11.96 ± 9.06 and L(II) was 14.19 ± 13.67 , which was significantly lower than the patients with L(III) with mean 107.64 ($p = 0.001$), and serum prolactin in L(I) was 18.26 ± 2.52 and L(II) was 21.24 ± 3.22 , which was significantly higher than the patients with L(III) where it was 13.7 ($p = 0.033$).

Case Pictures:

Figure 6: Showing Peripilar Sign in Patient with FPHL

Figure 7: Showing Hair Shaft Variability of more than 20% in Patients with FPHL

Figure 8: Showing Upright Regrowing Hair in A Patient with Acute Telogen Effluvium

Figure 9: Showing Multiple Single Follicular Unit in Frontal Scalp in Patient with FPHL.

Figure 10: Showing Vellus Hair on Vertex In Patient With FPHL.

Figure 11: Showing Yellow Dots

Figure 12: Showing Patient of FPHL (Ludwig II) With Intact Frontal Hairline

Figure 13: Showing Patient of FPHL With Temporal Hair Loss

Figure 14: Showing Patient with FPHL (Ludwig I)

Figure 15: Showing Patient of CTE with Temporal Hair Loss

Figure 16: Showing Patient of ATE with Diffuse Hair Loss

Figure 17: Showing Patient with Chronic Telogen Effluvium

Figure 18: Showing Daily Hair Shedding In Patient with Ate

Discussion

Diffuse hair loss is a very common condition for which female patients present to dermatology OPD. Although DHL has a better prognosis, it is still associated with significant psychological morbidity and has a major impact on quality of life.

In our study, a total of 133 patients who fulfilled inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled for evaluation of diffuse hair loss. In our study, the age of patients enrolled in our study ranged from 15 to 61, with a mean age of 36.66 ± 10.026 . The majority of the patients were in the age group 25-40 years (36.8%).

These results were comparable with the study conducted by Poonia Ket al. (2018), in which the maximum patient belonged to the age group 21-40 years (70%) [10]. Out of 133 patients, 73 (54.88%) patients were diagnosed as ATE, 42 (31.58%) as CTE, and 18 (13.54%) as FPHL. These results were comparable with the study conducted by Patel KB et al. (2014) and Jain VK et al. (2000) [11].

In our study, Pityriasis capitis was observed in 38.1% of the patients with CTE, which was comparable with the patients of ATE and FPHL, where it was observed in 32.9% and 16.7% patients, respectively. ($p = 0.35$). History of having a COVID-19 infection was present in 26% of the patients with ATE, which was significantly higher as compared to patients with FPHL (11.1%) and CTE (7.1%). ($p = 0.029$).

History of menstrual abnormality was present in 22.2% of the patients with FPHL, which was comparable with the patients with ATE and CTE, where it was noted in 6.9% and 9.5% of the patients, respectively. ($p = 0.22$).

Further, family history of diffuse hair loss was present in 66.7% of the patients with FPHL, which

was significantly higher as compared to patients with CTE (2.4%) and ATE (7.1%). ($p = 0.01$). This is in contrast with the study conducted by Siah TW et al. (2016), where only 4 patients (1.9%) had seborrheic dermatitis [12]. Dominguez-Santas M et al. (2020) were the first to report a case of acute TE, occurring 3 months after SARS-CoV-2 infection, and have been followed by many other authors who described TE after COVID-19 [13].

Similar results were seen in the study conducted by Quinn M et al. (2014), where they reported a PCOS prevalence among FPHL patients to be 22% [14]. Similar results were also seen in the study conducted by Lukasik A et al. (2020), where a positive family history was noted in 69 (62.2%) patients with FPHL [15].

In our study, a positive hair pull test indicative of telogen effluvium is present in 57 patients (78.1%) with acute telogen effluvium and 2 patients (4.76%) with chronic telogen effluvium, and it was negative in all the patients with FPHL. These results were comparable with the study conducted by Deo Ket al. (2016) [16].

The multifactorial aetiology and role of various laboratory parameters (Hb, PBF, serum Vit B12, serum Vit D3, TSH, serum f_eTin, LH, FSH, prolactin, and serum testosterone) in the pathogenesis of DHL is unclear, and there is paucity of research on this subject. Hence, in this study we intended to extend the research on the same.

In our study, it was found that laboratory parameters such as hemoglobin levels, S. ferritin, S. vitamin B12, and serum vitamin D3 were observed to be lower than the normal values in the majority of patients with ATE, CTE, and FPHL, whereas S. TSH was observed to be higher than the normal value in 37% of patients with ATE, 31%

with CTE, and 27.8% of the patients with FPHL. These results were comparable with the study conducted by Deo Ket al. (2016), Poonia Ket al. (2018), and Jayashankar CA et al. (2016) [16,10,17]. Specific etiological factors in ATE were found in 79.4% of patients, while in 20.6% no definite cause could be found. In our study, febrile illness was an etiological factor of hair loss in 30.13% of patients, while telogen gravidarum was found in 4.10% of patients, and psychological stress was found in 6.8% of patients. These results were in contrast with the studies where precipitating factors in the form of febrile illness for TE were found in 33% and 22% of the patients, telogen gravidarum was found in 21% and 10% of the patients, and psychological stress was found in 30% and 42% of the patients in the studies conducted by Jain VK et al. (2000) and Rustom A et al. (1994), respectively [18,19].

In our study of patients who were clinically suspected of hyperandrogenism, investigations revealed 55.6% of patients had deranged hormonal assays. Serum testosterone was elevated in 7 (38.8%) patients, serum LH and serum FSH were elevated in 10 (55.5%) patients, and serum prolactin was at the normal level in all the patients. The results of our study are in concordance with the studies conducted by Olsen EA et al. (2006) and Futtenteit W et al. (1988) (20, 21). In our study, we found the mean \pm SD of serum FSH in Ludwig I was 11.96 ± 9.06 and Ludwig II was 14.19 ± 13.67 , which was significantly lower than in patients with Ludwig III, where it was 107.64 ($p = 0.001$).

Conclusion

In our study most of the patients presented within 1 year of the duration of hair loss. The main contributory factor for acute telogen effluvium patients was febrile illness and severe anaemia. Serum ferritin, serum TSH, serum vitamin B12 and D3 levels seem to have a contributing role in the pathogenesis of hair loss, and their supplementation may be required for the faster hair growth in non-scanning DHL.

References:

- Patel KB, Gandhi AV, Patel RV, Shah VR, Pujara SB. A clinical and Investigative study of hair loss in adult female Int J Res Med. 2014; 3(4); 28- 36.
- Habif TP. Clinical Dermatology: A color guide to diagnosis and therapy. 5th edn. St. Louis: Mosby; 2010. Hair diseases. In: Habif TP, editor; pp. 920-22.
- Wadhwa SL, Khopkar U, Nischal KC. IADVL Textbook of dermatology. 3rd edn. Mumbai: Bhalani Publishing House; 2010. Hair and scalp disorders. In: Valia RG, Valia AR, editors; pp. 864-948.
- Steinberg S, Ezers IA. Alopecia in women. Can Physician. 1970; 16(4):64-66.
- Grover C, Khurana A. Telogen effluvium. Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol. 2013; 79:591-603.
- Harrison S, Sinclair R. Telogen effluvium. Clin Exp Dermatol. 2002; 27:389-85.
- Sinclair RD, Banfield CC, Dawber RP. Handbook of diseases of the hair and scalp. UK: Blackwell Science Ltd; 1999. Diffuse hair loss. In: Sinclair RD, Banfield CC, Dawber RP editors; pp. 64-74.
- Malkud S. A hospital-based study to determine causes of diffuse hair loss in women. J Clin Diagn Res 2015; 9(8):WC01-4.
- Harrison S, Sinclair R. Telogen effluvium. Clin Exp Dermatol 2002; 27(5):389-395.
- Poonia K, Thami G, Bhalla M, Jaiswal S, Sandhu J. Non Scanning Diffuse Hair Loss in Women: a Clinico Etiological Study from tertiary care center in No1th West India. J Cosmet Dermatol 2018; 18(1):401-407.
- Jain VK, Kataria U, Dayal S. Study of diffuse alopecia in females. Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol 2000; 66:65-68.
- Siah TW, Muir-Green L, Shapiro J. "Female Pattern Hair Loss: A Retrospective Study in a Tertiary Referral Center." International Journal of Trichology 2016; 8(2):57-
- Dominguez-Santas M, Haya-Martinez L, Fernandez-Nieto D, Jimenez-Cauhe J, Suarez-Valle A, Diaz-Guimaraens B. Acute telogen effluvium associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection. Aust J Gen Pract 2020;49:10.31128.
- Quinn M, Shinkai K, Pasch L, Kuzmich L, Cedai's M, Huddleston H. Prevalence of androgenic alopecia in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome and chai-factorization of associated clinical and biochemical features. Fertil Steril 2014; 101(4):1129-1134.
- Lukasik A, Kozicka K, Klosowicz A, Jaworek A, Wojas-Pelc A. The role of family hist01y and its influence on the onset time in female pattern hair loss. Postepy Dermatol Alergol 2021; 38(5):815-818.
- Deo K, Shai·ma YK, Wadhokai· M, Tyagi N. Clinicoepidemiological Observational Study of Acquired Alopecias in Females Copulating with Anemia and Thyroid Function. Dermatol Res Pract 2016; 2016:6279108.
- Jayashankar CA, Shailaja A, Prakash B, Shwetha HP. Hemoglobin, fe1Titin and thyroid profile in women with chronic telogen effluvium. International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences 2016; 4(1):152-155.
- Jain VK, Kataria U, Dayal S. Study of diffuse alopecia in females. Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol 2000; 66:65-68.
- Rustom A, Pasricha JS. Causes of diffuse alopecia in women. Indian Journal of Dermatolo-

- gy Venereology and Leprology. 1994; 60(5): 266.
20. Olsen EA, Messenger AG, Shapiro J, Bergfeld WF, Hordinsky MK, Roberts JL et al. Evaluation and treatment of male and female pattern hair loss. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2005; 52(2):301-311.
 21. Futterweit W, Dunaif A, Yeh HC, Kingsley P. The prevalence of hyperandrogenism in 109 consecutive female patients with diffuse alopecia. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology* 1988; 19(5):831-836.